

THE CURRENT STATE OF COOPERATION BETWEEN THE STATES OF THE REGION IN THE USE OF TRANSBOUNDARY WATERS IN CENTRAL ASIA

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<https://www.doi.org/10.37547/ejar-v03-i03-p1-03>

ARTICLE INFO

Received: 24th February 2023

Accepted: 28th February 2023

Online: 02nd March 2023

KEY WORDS

Transboundar, drinking water, environmental safety, transboundary rivers, climate change, Central Asia.

ABSTRACT

This article presents a scientific analysis of the issues of drinking water, transboundary rivers and dams, the study of the impact of hydropower use of water from transboundary rivers in Central Asia on the socio-economic development of the region's states and the environment.

This article also presents a number of proposals for the rational use of the waters of transboundary rivers in Central Asia, ensuring environmental safety, preventing the negative consequences of the construction of large hydropower facilities and solving hydropower problems.

In connection with the global water problem of the last decades of the XX century and the XXI century, large-scale research is being conducted in the field of rational and equitable use of transboundary waters, ensuring environmental safety of the environment, construction of hydraulic structures and reservoirs. In particular, the main issue of the specialists' attention was the study of the impact of the hydropower use of the waters of transboundary rivers in Central Asia on the socio-economic development and the environment of the states of the region. Not only national and local specialists, but also scientists, researchers and researchers from major foreign research centers and institutes take an active part in scientific research in this area.

The issue of drinking water, transboundary rivers and dams also regularly attracts the attention of the UN and its specialized agencies, the World Bank, ADB, CIS, SCO, African Development Bank, European Union, OSCE and other reputable international organizations. The UN World Water Resources Assessment Programme publishes the UN Universal Report every three years [1].

As a solution, a number of proposals can be put forward for the rational use of the waters of transboundary rivers in Central Asia, ensuring environmental safety of the environment, preventing the negative consequences of the construction of large hydropower facilities and solving hydropower problems. It is advisable to approach this issue from the point of view of the immediate and long-term perspective. In any case, these decisions should not undermine the energy potential of the States of the region, which are important for the national economy.

Experts express full confidence that the Convention can also play an important role in addressing the issues of the use of water resources of transboundary rivers in Central Asia. In particular, the report prepared by the Center for Water Law, Policy and Science at UNESCO (Netherlands) in cooperation with the University of Dundee (Scotland) and the non-governmental organization "Wildlife Fund" (WWF) states that all states of the Aral Sea basin refuse to join the UN Convention "On the Right of International Use of Open Water spaces by navigable route". D.Ziganshina believes that "the integration of all countries in the region will strengthen the legal and institutional foundations of cooperation in the field of transboundary water resources management and will contribute to the creation of an effective system of rational use of shared waters" [2].

The expert notes that the application of the provisions of the Convention in Central Asia has good prospects. Kazakhstan and Turkmenistan, which are parties to the 1992 United Nations Economic Commission for Europe Convention on Transboundary Open Watercourses and the International Convention on the Protection and Use of Lakes, may in the future, following the example of Uzbekistan, join the UN Convention on the Right to Use International Open Watercourses in Navigable Mode.

The Intergovernmental Agreement "On Cooperation in the Field of joint Management, Use and Protection of International Water Resources", signed by the leaders of the Central Asian countries in February 1992, today serves as the legal basis for joint management and distribution of water between consumers of the Aral Sea basin. In addition, in the next decade, the Central Asian countries adopted a number of bilateral and multilateral agreements and documents related to river basins, based on previously agreed water distribution schemes and the aforementioned treaty. At the same time, the basic principle of international water law, namely the "duty not to cause great harm", is still not respected by the States of the region, especially the countries located upstream. The necessary terms and concepts for the definition of interstate water resources have not yet been agreed between the countries of Central Asia [3].

As a result of global climate change, the area of glaciers in Central Asia has decreased by about 30 % over the past 50-60 years. It is estimated that with an increase in temperature by 20 C, the volume of glaciers decreases by 50 %, and with an increase in temperature by 40C- by 78 %.

It is expected that by 2050, water resources in the Sirdarya basin will decrease by 5%, and in the Amudarya basin - up to 15%. The total water deficit in Uzbekistan for the period up to 2015 amounted to more than 3 billion cubic meters, by 2030 it may reach 7 billion cubic meters, and by 2050 - 15 billion cubic meters [4].

In recent years, between the States of Central Asia, in particular, the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan Sh.Mirziyoyev's efforts and initiatives have improved water management relations between the republics of Turkmenistan, Kyrgyzstan and Tajikistan, and there has been a positive trend towards solving problems of transboundary water use.

However, in the future, the construction of new large hydropower facilities and reservoirs in the upper reaches of the Amudarya and Sirdarya, as well as the use of existing ones in the energy regime, may create a number of problems in the water supply of states located in the lower reaches of rivers, including Uzbekistan.

In addition, the development of new lands in subsequent years may negatively affect the balance of water distribution between the states of the region. This requires further improvement of the regional legal framework in the use of water resources of the Aral Sea basin. Therefore, the development of regional programs representing the interests of the States of the region is one of the urgent issues of today.

The construction of hydraulic structures causes transboundary, long-term, direct or indirect, interdisciplinary or boomerang negative impacts on the environment. That is, the scale of negative impacts is wide: they can cause serious problems not only for one state, but also for several other neighboring states in the river basin [5].

As a result of the development and adoption of the “regional program for the rational use of water resources in Central Asia” in order to prevent various risks arising in the future between the States of the region, the prevention of solving long-unresolved problems in this region was achieved.

It is known that the growing shortage of water resources from year to year as a result of climate change and the melting of glaciers, as well as the increase in the population of the region and, accordingly, the need for food and water are among the main problems of development and sustainability of the states of the region in the future. Today, Central Asian countries are facing problems related to water scarcity, water pollution and depletion of water sources. Industrialization, high demographic growth and the level of urbanization also lead to an increase in demand for water resources from year to year in the face of growing demand for food. According to statistics, currently in the region.

It is home to more than 70 million people, and this figure, according to UN estimates, as well as studies, could reach 94 million people in Central Asia by 2050. This, in turn, creates new problems associated with increased demand for food and water. Under these conditions, the Central Asian countries should take measures to strengthen and develop cooperation in the field of transboundary use of water resources, as well as on the efficient and rational use of water resources. Therefore, the main objective of the regional program for the rational use of water resources in Central Asia is to develop cooperation between the States of the region in the water sphere, unite efforts to solve common problems related to water resources and ensure the rational use of water resources in Central Asia, as well as the main objectives of this program are to strengthen regional cooperation and increase the efficiency of water use in the Aral Sea basin. Development of mutually acceptable mechanisms; improvement of water accounting and control mechanisms, improvement of information exchange on water resources; development of water conservation system, taking measures to improve the efficiency of water resources use; development of proposals to improve the organizational and legal framework of regional water cooperation.

Scientific analysis suggests that when using the water of transboundary rivers, the construction of dams and reservoirs, it is necessary to take into account:

Firstly, the condition for a clear definition of the mode of use of waterworks at the stage of planning and designing the construction of waterworks and reservoirs on transboundary rivers is;

Secondly, interstate, intergovernmental and interdepartmental bilateral and multilateral treaties and agreements on the use of water resources of the Amudarya and Sirdarya basins in

the region are combined into single international legal acts “On the use of water resources of the Amudarya basin between the Government of the Republic of Tajikistan, the Government of the Republic of Uzbekistan, the Government of the Islamic Republic of Afghanistan and the Government of Turkmenistan”. The Convention on Consumer Rights Protection “The Government of the Republic of Tajikistan, the Government of the Republic of Uzbekistan, the Convention between the Government of the Republic of Kazakhstan and the Government of the Kyrgyz Republic on the Use of Water Resources of the Sirdarya basin”.

Thirdly, the implementation of power steering with the help of artificial intelligence is a requirement of today. Improvement of water resources management mechanisms, processing and strengthening of environmental standards give positive results with intensive water use. Following the example of Uzbekistan,

In 2020, as a result of a man-made disaster, tank tanks were flooded not only our country, but also some areas of neighboring Kazakhstan.

Also, in conditions of increasing energy scarcity, it is necessary to further enrich international contractual instruments on the use of transboundary river waters for energy purposes, the construction of large hydropower facilities, assessment of their transboundary impact and elimination of consequences, as well as strengthening mechanisms for their execution and control.

The convergence of the national legislation of neighboring States in the use of transboundary open watercourses and the harmonization of legal policy in this area facilitate the process of implementing the norms of international law into national legal systems. In this regard, it is advisable to expand international legal cooperation between the legislature and responsible State bodies.

It is worth noting here that consistent international cooperation between the States of the region and the heads of Government, based on mutual trust and respect, is the key to success.

As another proposal, the Helsinki Convention “On the Protection and Use of Transboundary Open Watercourses and International Lakes”, adopted on March 17, 1992, should be fully implemented into national legislation regulating the use of water by the States of the region (Uzbekistan, Kazakhstan and Turkmenistan), as well as the construction and safety of hydraulic structures. In particular, the Helsinki Convention contains norms on public awareness (Article 16), i.e. riparian parties should ensure that the public is informed about the state of transboundary waters, measures taken or planned to prevent, control and reduce transboundary impacts, as well as the effectiveness of these measures.

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